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UKRAINE'S SUCCESSFUL PATH IN THE CIVILIZATIONAL DIRECTION?..

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Abstract

The scientific approach involves considering any process from the point of view of cause-and-effect relationships. For example, you need to start by identifying the causes and why they arose in the first place, and then find ways to eliminate these causes, and not just deal with the consequences.

In all social and socio-economic processes (even the emergence of economic crises) there is mainly one reason, this is the behavior of people. And the behavior of people, in turn, is determined by two factors: the first is what kind of human and professional qualities a person is, and the second is the rules of the behavioral "game" dictated by the management system.

Ukraine has not used any of the main postulates of the scientific approach, which causes its gradual decline to the backyards of Europe.

The authors propose ways to improve this situation that will be beneficial for Ukraine and for the whole world.

Keywords: civilizational direction of development, prosperity, behavior of elites, human-centeredness, self-realization of the individual, a new course of post-war Ukraine.

Foreword. Ukraine's path to prosperity turns out to be long and difficult, for more than 30 years of independence, it is still unclear whether we are moving forward or backward compared to the Ukrainian SSR. It is even more unclear where exactly we are going, and whether we have a clear goal, except for hackneyed slogans like "to ensure Well-being for everyone and Dignity".

The vision of the falsity of the movement towards progress began to gradually form among concerned domestic scientists-analysts during the first five years of Ukraine's independence. This was served by the unprofessional actions of the government to ensure economic reforms, which led to the disappearance of the fishing fleet, the seizure of enterprises and the outflow of large sums of money to foreign banks, and much more.

Therefore, it is necessary to start with the definition of "Where should post-war Ukraine go to", so that the path to the future wasn't to be found blindly ("at random").

Presentation of the main material of the study.

The scientific approach involves considering any process from the point of view of cause-and-effect relationships. For example, you need to start by identifying the causes and why they arose in the first place, and then find ways to eliminate these causes, and not just deal with the consequences.

In all social and socio-economic processes (even the emergence of economic crises) there is mainly one reason, this is the behavior of people. And the behavior of people, in turn, is determined by two factors: the first is what a person is in terms of his human and profes-

sional qualities, and the second is the rules of the behavioral "game" dictated by the management system. It is formed by the extractive (backward) or inclusive (progressive) ruling elite. "What are the qualities of people", this applies, first of all, to representatives of the managerial elite of political and economic institutions that dictate the rules for the behavioral activity of all people in a particular country.

Volodymyr Vernadsky was the first to come to the conclusion that the biosphere in the process of combining human labor with scientific and technological progress generated by it gradually passes into a new state called The Noosphere, that is, the sphere of the mind. The noosphere acts as a set of knowledge accumulated by mankind over the millennia of its existence and is the repository of all wisdom on planet Earth.

Due to the continuous chain of scientific inventions and innovative transformations (which are carried out in the process of people's creative activity), the biosphere is more and more filled with a body of knowledge, when new knowledge is superimposed on knowledge from the past [2].

Today, the world resembles chaos as a consequence of an imperfect civilization (an organic part of which is the wild fact of Russia's aggression). Many Ukrainian scientists, in search for the optimal path of Ukraine to progress, turned to the higher noosphere mind, already accumulated by humanity [3; 4; 5; 6].

At the same time, simply turning to the noosphere and referring to eternal wisdom is clearly not enough – they are all scattered and have only a generalizing character. At the same time, any course is not a set of slogans that is offered in the programs of almost all

Ukrainian parties. A course is a set of strategy (with a clearly defined end goal) and specific technologies for its implementation. In particular, through obtaining clear measured final results of the activities of government structures.

This tells us the eternal managerial wisdom, which belongs to the outstanding philosopher of antiquity, Aristotle: *"Good under any circumstances depends on the observance of two conditions: the first of them is the correct definition of the task and the ultimate goal of any kind of activity; the second is to find various means that will lead to the achievement of the ultimate goal"* [7, p. 612].

That is, first you need to find the right goal and tools for measuring the final results that characterize the achievement of the goal.

More and more the Ukrainian people are convinced of the inability of the authorities to realize their purpose to serve the people, subordinating their egocentrism to public interests: corruption is spreading, inequality in society is growing, more and more people want to go abroad, etc.

If these painful components of the general "disease" are clearly defined, it becomes possible to cure the entire disease. A thorough analysis of the realities of 30 years of development of independent Ukraine, as well as its recent and ancient history, made it possible to identify seven such key pain points, which are given below.

Components of the problem of inefficiency of the Ukrainian government.

- A blind movement towards progress since 1991.
- Invincible corruption as a tangle of intertwined ties.
- Public administration system without feedback; is not focused on improving the quality of human life.
- The immaturity of civil society as a means of influencing power from below from the people.
- Negative mental human qualities from the past in a large stratum of the population, from the active share of which the managerial elite is formed according to a distorted electoral system.
- The bureaucratized education system is helpless in the absence of defined end results in all management structures, starting with the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine and ending with educational institutions.
- Lack of vision of the connection between the Ukrainian path to progress and the movement of all mankind towards a harmonious civilization.

World experience shows that the problem of authorities has long been known, but it has always been another, some distant authorities. And this is its own, suffered, but it destroys all opportunities for Ukraine to become a prosperous state.

Not everyone knows and remembers the main principle of social justice of any society, which Lee Kuan Yew followed during the socio-economic miracle in Singapore and which at one time was the proclaimed main principle of socialism. This principle originates

from Confucius, according to which in a harmonious society "every individual has his own function".

Henry Ford sought to implement this principle at his enterprises [8]. It is this principle that all democratic countries of the world are trying to follow with their capitalist system with a "human face", creating conditions for a decent life and decent remuneration for work for everyone.

But proclaiming is one thing, and putting it into practice is quite another. The fact is that the implementation of this principle is based on finding means of measuring, first of all, the results of work not only of workers, but also of the entire galaxy of mental and managerial workers, including the heads of any organizations. And if such a remedy were found, then let's imagine what representatives of the ex-Communist Party managerial elite would look like if the final results of their activities related to the quality of people's lives were constantly deteriorating.

From the noosphere point of view on the implementation of the highest principle of social justice (from everyone according to their abilities, to each according to their work), it is enough to solve three problems. First: to help each person determine their abilities at school (through the joint efforts of parents and teachers). Second: to find a universal method for evaluating the results of work (activity). Third: to link the first with the second through the management mechanism on an appropriate economic and legal basis.

But we must expect that there will be a lot of resistance from the side on this path... from the authorities themselves. Its representatives are already accustomed to the "black" filters of access to the managerial elite (money, connections, agreeableness), and as for the abilities and evaluation of a person by the final results of activity, these arguments faded into the background.

It was the absence, first of all, of the authorities' responsibility for these results in the context of violation of the main principle of social justice (within the framework of the economic managerial culture of administrative pressure from the past) that caused the low quality of the managerial elite in Ukraine after 1991.

Therefore, in no case should we repeat this mistake from the past. It is imperative to find and apply in practice a uniquely universal method of assessing the resulting activities of the authorities, in order to link this assessment with the social and economic status of representatives of the managerial elite. This, among other things, will be an extremely important proof of the first Article of the Constitution of Ukraine, that it really *"is... a social, legal state"* [9].

The experience of economically developed democratic countries has proven that it is a developed civil society that is able to curb the egocentrism of those in authority and orient their activities (under pressure from the people) for the benefit of people. At the same time, the study of this phenomenon of civil society made it possible to identify two models of its formation, which can also complement each other.

The first model includes the systematic holding of referendums of national and regional nature several times a year with the obligatory execution of their decisions by the authorities, which is legally enshrined. In

addition, the openness of the decisions of the government structures, plus the holding of various kinds of plebiscites and discussions of decisions made by the authorities at different levels, complement the current model of civil society in Switzerland, which, with its multilingual and multiethnic population, has been demonstrating unity and cohesion within the country for centuries without any hint of confrontation between the authorities and the people [10].

The second model was actively developing in the United States. Its essence lies in a large number of public organizations that can control the activities of government structures, which is confirmed at the legislative level. There are more than 1.5 million such organizations in the United States.

After 1991, Ukraine adopted this model, but distorted it in a strange way. We are talking about public organizations (NGOs), which for the most part began to be formed by the authorities themselves. As a result, these NGOs turned into shams (exclusively for the formal coordination of government decisions). Also, nothing came of the combination of the Swiss model of civil society with the model of the United States. In Ukraine, even once, on December 1, 1991, a Referendum was held. President Volodymyr Zelenskyy's attempt to hold a second... failed.

Thus, Ukraine faces the problem of finding its own technology for combining the interests of the people and the government, relying, to a certain extent, on the experience of developed countries, which, as we can see, does not fully "work" in the conditions of immature Ukrainian democracy.

In the authors' opinion, Ukraine needs to introduce a tougher model, more empathetic to people, capable of directly assessing the resulting actions of the authorities by the people to squeeze out of those in authority their inflated egocentrism (the origin of which comes from the past) and direct their activities for the benefit of people.

What is the importance of measuring the quality of life of citizens as an indicator of the resulting activity of government structures? We can say unequivocally – extraordinary. And it is in the conditions of Ukraine, where it is necessary to radically change not only the relations between representatives of the government and the people, but also in a certain way to change the inner world of both through the displacement of the consequences of the past.

What does the concept of "quality of life of citizens" include? Not at all the standard of living, which is characterized by a system of statistical indicators (with the average temperature in the hospital). The essence of QLS is in the level of satisfaction of a person's needs from the point of view of how he perceives it internally. Such perception is purely individual and subjective for each person. But its peculiarity lies in the fact that if there are more than 50 people, then the set of assessments of the level of QLS gives an objective result and can serve as an indicator of the resulting actions of the authorities.

It is necessary to divide all needs into general and purely individual. The former is within the competence of the authorities, and the latter are more often within

the personal competence of the person himself. The former contributes (or poorly contributes) to a person's self-realization in four spheres of his life: work, at the place of residence and recreation, studying in educational institutions, and living in a country that you should be proud of. The actions of the authorities, either directly or indirectly, necessarily affect the level of self-realization of the individual in these four areas.

Not everyone yet knows that the indicator of the quality of life of a person is an organic component of his happiness in the context of self-realization of the individual in all 5 spheres of life, including the sphere of personal life (in particular, being in a harmonious marriage). The latter already depends on the degree of self-knowledge of "Him" and "Her" of one's own "I". The importance of such self-knowledge was confidently argued (with reference to Buddhism) by Yuval Noah Harari, arguing that knowledge of the truth about oneself has a powerful basis for a person's personal happiness [11, p. 495].

If we consider the issue of the quality of life of citizens from the point of view of the degree of their self-realization in 5 spheres of life (the 5th is the sphere of personal life), then it makes sense to think about how this can be improved with the help of innovative education.

Sphere of "Labor activity". A person is self-realized in this area when he is happy to go to work, because there he will find interesting ("kindred") work with decent remuneration, recognition by management, an excellent microclimate, the opportunity for personal development and career growth, etc.

To get all this, it is necessary that education helps to determine the "related" work and not only provides professional knowledge and skills, but also that this knowledge is assimilated at a reflective level due to developed analytical and cognitive activity (ACA). At the same time, the ACA should be formed from the kindergarten with the involvement of parents.

And in order to achieve a good microclimate, everyone in society must respect each other, having a high level of universal human morality (UHM). This level is also formed in preschool education with the involvement of parents and is the foundation of conflict-free relationships in any society.

Sphere "At the place of residence and recreation". Here, the self-realization of people is carried out thanks to the actions of the authorities, the role of education is important in two aspects. First of all, in the formation of a capable managerial elite in the context of competence, decency, patriotism. Secondly, to help people in self-knowledge of their own "I" and their needs, to develop the ability to compare the latter with the needs of societies.

Sphere "Studying in educational institutions". Here, the role of education in human self-realization begins with meeting the needs of students in a friendly atmosphere of stay and curiosity of learning. The main task of education is to teach them to learn throughout life and live together in a multicultural society, ensuring the competitiveness of school graduates and the

competitiveness of graduates of higher educational institutions, including through instilling in them an interest in self-knowledge of their own "I".

The field of "Living in a country that you should be proud of". Self-realization of people in this area is associated with satisfying the needs in the vision of Ukraine as an authoritative state among other European countries and not only, which has a strategy for its peaceful development that is understandable to people. Regarding the internal state of the country, this need for self-realization concerns the well-established system of social justice, including the non-corrupt activities of the authorities, as well as all law enforcement agencies, courts and prosecutor's offices, etc.

Here, the role of education is extremely important in terms of promoting social justice through the active development of universal human morality (UHM) and the awakening of interest in self-knowledge of each of their own "I", as well as a positive impact on the formation of a worthy managerial elite capable of devoting itself to serving the people.

Sphere of "Personal Life". The essential role of education here also lies in the formation of a person who knows the truth about himself (which is the main basis for mutual happiness) and has a highly developed universal human morality as a fundamental guarantee of respect for each other in the family. Self-knowledge of one's own "I" adds more opportunities for self-improvement in search of compatibility of characters, values, etc.

Therefore, the importance of education can hardly be overestimated in the context of promoting human self-realization in all spheres of life. But there is one but. This can be achieved if human-centeredness becomes the ideology of the authorities' activities at all hierarchical levels, from local to national.

Conclusions and suggestions. According to the authors, the outline of the New Course of post-war Ukraine with its own "face" should consist of parts "reformatted" into a single integrity – the New Human-Centered Managerial Course of Post-War Ukraine in the context of civilizational development of mankind. Each of the parts is a separate pain point of the general "disease": helpless ineffective authorities.

Each of these components of the general "disease" of the government and the nation in general is a problem in itself. And we need to find a solution for each of them in the context of solving one extremely important problem for Ukraine: building a prosperous Ukraine with happy people and a developed economy under the leadership of a capable managerial elite, which is formed on the principle of meritocracy (according to merit).

Ukraine did not use any of these basic postulates of the scientific approach, which caused the decline to the backyards of Europe, because it never managed to find the end of the thread, namely the quality of authorities, "clinging" to the modernization of which everything could be changed for the better. This is what Singapore did after the proclamation of its independence, also obtained without bloodshed, but after a political struggle. *"First, to restore order in one's own country, then to make efforts to overcome the hostility of one's*

neighbors and ethnic differences inside, achieving good results in one's development" [1, P. 5-6].

There are two directions for improving the activities of government structures. The first of them is the presence of professional and human qualities of representatives of the managerial elite in political and economic institutions, which determine their ability to perform their functions in high government positions. The second is the culture of system management based on the final results with feedback.

But if you concentrate on the development of these specific technologies, there will be only one thing left, it is to find levers for their implementation through influence on the authorities either from below, or from the sides, or from above (the latter provided if Ukrainian own Lee Kuan Yew's appears).

This is exactly the development that scientists from the future Intellect Club have been engaged in since 1997. Let's imagine that we managed to digitally measure the level of quality of life of citizens (and then happiness) for each year of living in the communities of each village, town, city. And this is by conducting a specific annual survey of the population like a referendum (after all, its purpose is the same, to show the way from the people, where should the authorities move next...). **And most importantly, to officially determine the assessment of the quality of life of citizens by an annual assessment of the final results of the authorities' activities!** But it is even difficult to realize what advantages Ukraine will receive as a result of the modernization of its outdated corrupt state system in the conditions of clear responsibility of the authorities to their people! And this is a real return of managerial power "faced" to the people; and a significant weakening of corruption; and the unity of the interests of the government and the people; and an increase in the self-sufficiency of people; and their liberation from the role of "cogs" and objects of manipulation by politicians; and the possibility of implementing the principle of meritocracy at the same time. formation of the managerial elite and much more.

In the context of the theory of system management, in this case, the thesis of effective management is confirmed when establishing clear feedback in the public administration mechanism.

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